

Studies on the Coordination Polymer of Niobium(V) with 1,6-Dihydroxyphenazine

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Complexation reaction between niobium(V) and 1,6-dihydroxyphenazine has been investigated with a view to isolate the brown complex and to study its stoichiometry on the basis of elemental analysis, ir spectra, magnetic studies and thermogravimetric analysis. Infrared spectra show 1,6-dihydroxyphenazine acting as a tetradentate ligand coordinating through oxygen and nitrogen since two oxine functions are present in the structure of the ligand. A possible polymeric structure of the complex involving ligand and anion bridge has been suggested

Need for new polymeric material with good thermal and chemical stability has led to research on many coordination polymers since it is known that reaction of metal ions with organic ligands produces coordinated systems having enhanced thermal stability and often improved chemical resistance.

Studies on the coordination polymers of several metals with tetradentate 1,6-dihydroxyphenazine (DHP) have been reported in literature¹. Since several Nb(V) compounds have also been found to have polymeric structure, it was considered worthwhile to investigate reaction of DHP with niobium(V) also. Since two oxine functions are present in the ligand, complexation with DHP was expected to lead to interesting coordination products.

Experimental

Pure niobium pentachloride (Fluka) and A. R. grade chemicals were used

Preparation of niobium solution Niobium pentachloride (10 mole) was dissolved in a mixture of dimethylformamide and alcohol (1:1). Care was taken to avoid moisture while weighing.

Preparation of the reagent The reagent was obtained from 1,6-dimethoxyphenazine² by refluxing the product with hydrobromic and glacial acetic acids for 24 hr³. Golden-yellow needles were obtained after two crystallizations from ethylacetate. The compound does not show any sharp melting point and decomposed at 274-275°. Found: C, 67.42; H, 3.75; N, 13.01. $C_{12}H_8O_2N$ requires C, 67.90; H, 3.78; N, 13.70%.

Preparation of the coordination polymer: An equimolar mixture of 1,6-dihydroxyphenazine and niobium pentachloride was refluxed in an alcohol-dimethylformamide (1:1) mixture for about 2-3 hr. The brown precipitate obtained was filtered and washed with alcohol-DMF mixture and dried at room temperature. The complex does not show a sharp melting point. It is not soluble in common organic solvents like acetone, benzene, chloroform, nitrobenzene, pyridine etc.

Elemental analysis: The chief constituents of the complex were determined by standard methods. The molecular weight of the complex could not be determined because of its insolubility in common organic solvents. Found C, 21.51; H, 0.98; N, 3.92; Cl, 40.98; M, 27.02. $(C_{12}H_8N_2O_2Nb_2Cl_6)_n$ requires C, 21.18; H, 0.88; N, 4.11; Cl, 41.77; M, 27.33%.

IR spectra: The ir spectra of 1,6-dihydroxyphenazine show characteristic frequencies pertaining to -OH, -C-N and aromatic characters. The phenolic -OH stretching absorption bands are found in the region 1110 cm^{-1} , 1260 cm^{-1} and 1350 cm^{-1} ; -C=N- absorption peak is found in the region 1650 cm^{-1} , 1560 cm^{-1} and 1280 cm^{-1} . The spectra of the complex is discussed later.

Magnetic studies Magnetic susceptibility of the complex was measured by Gouy method using mercury(II) tetrathiocyanate cobaltate(II) as the calibrating agent ($\chi_g - 16.44 \times 10^{-5}$ cgs units) at 300 K. Pascal's constants were used to correct the measured susceptibility for the diamagnetism of the cation and the ligand⁴. The magnetic moment of the complex was found to be 0.41 B.M. (300°K)

Thermogravimetric analysis Setaram G-70 Thermoanalyzer (France) was used to study the thermal stability of the coordination polymer. The sample in the 50 mg range was carefully weighed in a platinum crucible and positioned in the centre of furnace. Heating was carried out in oxygen atmosphere. During the entire run the temperature in the immediate vicinity of the sample and weight loss were recorded on previously calibrated chart paper. The per cent weight loss was plotted as a function of temperature. The TG analysis indicates that the complex is stable till 230°. The initial degradation takes place between 230-530°, possibly due to the partial decomposition of the polymer and formation of some oxide. Finally at 530° the polymer is completely converted into niobium pentoxide.

Results and Discussion

Coordination of niobium(V) with 1,6-dihydroxyphenazine is presumed to form a coordination polymer having a possible structure represented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

The ir spectra of the polymer is in close conformity with the above structure.

Significant changes were observed in the spectra of the ligand after complex formation. Phenolic-OH stretching and bending vibrations are absent. The M-O bond is assigned at 925 cm^{-1} in the same way as attributed to the chelate of 8-hydroxyquinoline⁶. The frequency of -C=N vibration in the complex spectra is shifted to lower regions. These suggest involvement of hydroxyl group and N atom in the coordination with the niobium atom.

The terminal Nb-Cl stretching band appears at 342 cm^{-1} . Similar frequency at $340\text{-}270\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been reported for such bond in some other niobium octahedral complexes⁶. Many bands appear in the spectra of the complex at 240 cm^{-1} , 220 cm^{-1} suggesting M-Cl bridging since, in general, bridging M-Cl stretching frequencies are lower than terminal M-Cl stretching frequency⁷. Increase in the coordination number as well as polymeric structure is also considered responsible for the lowering of the bridging frequencies⁸.

The insolubility of the complex in common solvents and lowering of bridging M-Cl frequencies lend support to the polymeric nature of the complex as is, in fact, found in the case of polymeric structure of NbOCl_2 ⁹.

Interpretation of magnetic susceptibility of the compound of second and third row transition series is more complex since the 4d and 5d orbitals are larger than the 3d orbitals so that the inter-electronic repulsions which tend to oppose spin

pairing are less. Also, since the nuclear charges are higher and therefore exert stronger attraction on the ligands, a given set of ligands produces a greater splitting of the d orbitals. The Nb-DHP complex is diamagnetic and the effective magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) has been found to be 0.41 B.M. (300 K). This is far below the purely spin value for an unpaired electron (1.73 B. M.), since the spin orbital effects should be negligible. Thus the little μ_{eff} may be due to only spin-spin interaction between niobium atoms through the chlorine bridge. A number of complexes are reported which are apparently dimeric or polymeric and show only a small paramagnetism¹⁰.

The results of elemental analysis considered along with the ir spectra and magnetic studies indicate the complex to be a linear coordination polymer. Though the thermal stability of this polymer is not high yet its insolubility in common solvents is noteworthy.

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